

Avifauna checklist of Tillari, Chandgad Taluk, Kolhapur, Southern Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports a total of 174 bird species representing 20 orders, 59 families and 133 genera sighted during eighteen months survey in Tillari and its vicinity of Chandgad taluk in Kolhapur, Maharashtra. Accipitridae represents maximum (12) number of bird species followed by Muscicapidae (9) and Motacillidae (8). Among the orders Passeriformes alone represent 49.43% of the total bird species recorded followed by Falconiformes (8.05%), Ciconiformes, Charadriiformes and Columbiformes (5.75% each). Out of total birds recorded 79% resident, 20% winter visitor and 1% is summer visitor. Among the bird species sighted 89% were found least concerned, 3 % were near threatened and Nilgiri Wood Pigeon *Columba elphinstonii* is the only species belongs to vulnerable category.

Keywords: Avifauna checklist, Tillari, Damni dam, Chandgad, Passeriformes

INTRODUCTION

Maharashtra represents 618 bird species of 1300 plus found in Indian subcontinent consisting rare, exotic, native, endangered and endemic birds. There are several reports on avifauna checklist from Maharashtra. To mention few Prasad (2003) reported 450 birds from Western Maharashtra, Pachlore and Chandrashekar (2011) documented 97 bird species from Amarawati, Narwade and fartade (2011) recorded 165 birds from Osmanabad. Since, Chandgad is a part of Western Ghats preliminary observations are made by Hiragond and Gavade (2012), Hiragond *et al.*, (2013, 2015,) Hiragond and Lokhande (2015) and, Lokhande *et al.*, (2013) to record the avifauna biodiversity. Further, efforts are made to prepare avifauna checklist of Tillari forest and its vicinity in Chandgad (latitude 15° 45' to 16° 3' North & longitude 74° 1' to 74° 27' East) taluk of Kolhapur in southern Maharashtra.

Material and Methods

Study area:

Tillari is located around 762 m above sea level and temperature ranging from 14.75 to 36.10° C. It receives heavy rains between 3000 to 5000 mm/year. Habitat consists of 3B/C2, South moist mixed deciduous forest and 2A/C2, West coast semi evergreen mixed forest with acacia plantation, bamboo forest, open land, grass land, temporary and permanent water bodies, several irrigation canals and streams in forest. Study area consist Tillari (Damni) dam which supplies water for drinking, irrigation and for hydroelectric purposes. Study area consists several trees viz., Mango (*Mangifera indica*), Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*), Margosa (*Azadirachta indica*), Acacia (*Acacia longifolia*), Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*), Bamboo (*Bambusa vulgaris*), Ficus (*Ficus benghalensis* and *Ficus racemosa*), Ashok (*Polyalthia longifolia*), Teak (*Tectona grandis*) and xerophytic plants like Cactus (*Opuntia dillenii*), Aloe (*Aloe vera*), Calotropis (*Calotropis gigantea*) etc. *Cymbopogon gidarba* and *Cymbopogon martinii* are the common grass varieties found in open lands.

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Methods:

Regular field visits were made to document the avifauna in Tillari and its vicinity Parle, Konalkatta near power project, Tillari (Damni) reservoir and adjacent forest in Chandgad. Study area was explored travelling on two wheeler vehicle as well as on foot. Survey was made for the period of 18 months from August 2011 to January 2013. For documentation of avifauna in few places we have applied point transact count method. Survey was made along the road side, inside the forest, forest edge, along the edge of water bodies and streams in forest, open lands, bamboo forest, acacia plantation, grass land and in agricultural fields. Birds observed by opportunistic sighting also added to the checklist. Direct observations were made by using 10 x 50 X Olympus binocular during peak activity of birds between 6.00 to 11.00 am and 3.30 to 6.30 pm. We took some photographs of birds for identification. Birds were identified on the field using field guides by Ali (2002), Kazmierczak (2000), Grimmett and Inskipp (2007) and Grimmett *et al.* (1998, 2011). The Common and scientific names of birds is followed after Grimmett *et al.* (2011). Status of threatened category of birds is adopted from IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (2012) and BirdLife International (2013). Migratory status of birds was categorized in to resident (R), winter visitor (VW) and summer visitor (SW). Only confirmed species are added to the checklist.

Results and Discussion

Above said survey resulted in documentation of

174 bird species representing 20 orders, 59 families and 133 genera (Table 1). Accipitridae family consist maximum (12) number of bird species followed by Muscipidae (9) and Motacillidae (8). Other families with number of bird species recorded are Ardeidae, Scolopacidae and Timaliidae-6 species each; Phasianidae, Cuculidae, Strigidae, Turdidae and Nectariniidae-5 species each; Bucerotidae, Hirundinidae, Pycnonotidae, Cisticolidae and Sturnidae-4 species each; Ramphastidae, Campephagidae, Dicuridae, Corvidae and Estrildidae-3 species each. Rests of the families represent two or one bird species (Table 2). Among the orders Passeriformes represent 49.43% (86) of the total bird species recorded (Figure 1). Other orders with number of bird species recorded are Falconiformes-14 (8.05%); Ciconiiformes, Charadriiformes and Columbiformes - 10 (5.75%) species each; Coraciiformes-6 (3.45%); Galliformes, Cuculiformes, Strigiformes and Piciformes - 5 (2.87%) species each; Bucerotiformes-4 (2.30%); Pelicaniformes-3 (1.72%); Gruiformes, Psittaciformes and Caprimulgiformes-2 (1.15%) species each; Anseriformes, Podicipediformes, Apodiformes, Upupiformies and Trogoniformes-one (0.57%) species each. In present observations 138 (79.31%) bird species found resident, 34 (19.54%) were winter visitor and 02 (1.15%) were summer visitor (Figure 2).

Out of total bird species sighted in present study 155 (89.08%) are least concerned. Black-headed Ibis *Threskiornis melanocephalus*, Darter *Anhinga melanogaster*, River Tern *Sterna aurantia*, Malabar Pied Hornbill *Anthracoceros coronatus* and Great Hornbill *Buceros bicornis* are near threatened (05,

Figure-1. Showing order wise number of bird species recorded in Tillari and its vicinity

Figure-2. Showing migratory status of bird species recorded in Tilari and its vicinity

2.87%) and Nilgiri Wood Pigeon *Columba elphinstonii* is the only species belongs to vulnerable category (IUCN, 2012 and BirdLife International, 2013). For 12 species IUCN assessment is not available (Table. 1).

In the study area hornbills were regularly observed in singly, in pair and in 3-10 individual flocks. Almost on every field trip to Tillari we sighted Malabar pied hornbill and other hornbills nearby road side, irrigation canal and water stream. We also

Table 1. Showing avifauna recorded in Tillari and its vicinity

Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	
				Migratory	IUCN
1. Order GALLIFORMES					
1	1.Phasianidae	Grey Junglefowl	<i>Gallus sonneratii</i>	R	LC
2		Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	R	LC
3		Red Spurfowl	<i>Galloperdix spadicea</i>	R	LC
4		Jungle Bush Quail	<i>Perdica asiatica</i>	R	LC
5		Common Quail	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	WV	LC
2. Order ANSERIFORMES					
6	2.Anatidae	Indian Spot-billed Duck	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	R	LC
3. Order PODICIPEDIFORMES					
7	3.Podicipedidae	Little Grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	R	LC
4. Order CICONIIFORMES					
8	4.Ciconiidae	Woolly-necked Stork	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	R	LC
9		Asian Openbill	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	WV	LC
10	5. Threskiornithidae	Red-naped Ibis	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	R	LC
11		Black-headed Ibis	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	R	NT
12	6.Ardeidae	Indian Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	R	LC
13		Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	R	LC
14		Intermediate Egret	<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	R	LC
15		Great Egret	<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	R	LC
16		Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	WV	LC
17		Purple Heron	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	R	LC
5. Order PELICANIFORMES					
18	7.Anhingidae	Darter	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i>	WV	NT

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Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	
				Migratory	IUCN
19	8.Phalacrocoracidae	Little Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	WV	LC
20		Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	WV	LC
6. Order FALCONIFORMES					
21	9.Falconidae	Common Kestrel	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	WV	LC
22		Peregrine Falcon	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	R	LC
23	10.Accipitridae	Brahminy Kite	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	R	LC
24		Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	R	LC
25		Black-winged Kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	R	LC
26		Crested Serpent Eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	R	LC
27		Bonelli's Eagle	<i>Aquila fasciata</i>	R	NA
28		Tawny Eagle	<i>Aquila rapax</i>	R	LC
29		Oriental Honey-buzzard	<i>Pernis ptilorhynchus</i>	R	LC
30		White-eyed Buzzard	<i>Butastur teesa</i>	R	LC
31		Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	R	LC
32		Crested Hawk Eagle	<i>Nisaetus cirrhatus</i>	R	LC
33		Black Eagle	<i>Ictinaetus malayensis</i>	R	LC
34		Short-toed Snake Eagle	<i>Circaetus gallicus</i>	R	LC
7. Order GRUIFORMES					
35	11.Rallidae	White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	R	LC
36		Eurasian Coot	<i>Fulica atra</i>	R	LC
8. Order CHARADRIIFORMES					
37	12.Burhinidae	Indian Thick-knee	<i>Burhinus indicus</i>	R	NA
38	13.Charadriidae	Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	R	LC
39		Yellow-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus malabaricus</i>	WV	LC
40	14.Scolopacidae	Common Sandpiper	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	WV	LC
41		Wood Sandpiper	<i>Tringa glareola</i>	WV	LC
42		Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	WV	LC
43		Common Greenshank	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	WV	LC
44		Marsh Sandpiper	<i>Tringa stagnatilis</i>	WV	LC
45		Little Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	R	LC
46	15.Laridae	River Tern	<i>Sterna aurantia</i>	R	NT
9. Order COLUMBIFORMES					
47	16.Columbidae	Common Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	R	LC
48		Nilgiri Wood Pigeon	<i>Columba elphinstonii</i>	R	V
49		Laughing Dove	<i>Stigmatopelia senegalensis</i>	R	LC
50		Spotted Dove	<i>Stigmatopelia chinensis</i>	R	LC
51		Emerald Dove	<i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	R	LC
52		Red Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	R	LC
53		Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	R	LC
54		Oriental Turtle Dove	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i>	WV	LC
55		Yellow-footed Green Pigeon	<i>Treron phoenicopterus</i>	R	LC
56		Grey-fronted Green Pigeon	<i>Treron affinis</i>	R	NA
10. Order PSITTACIFORMES					
57	17.Psittacidae	Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	R	LC
58		Plum-headed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	R	LC
11. Order CUCULIFORMES					
59	18.Cuculidae	Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	R	LC
60		Southern Coucal	<i>Centropus parroti</i>	R	NA
61		Common Hawk Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	R	NA
62		Drongo Cuckoo	<i>Surniculus lugubris</i>	R	LC
63		Grey-bellied Cuckoo	<i>Cacomantis passerinus</i>	R	LC

.....Table 1. Showing avifauna recorded in Tillari and its vicinity

Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	
				Migratory	IUCN
12. Order STRIGIFORMES					
64	19.Strigidae	Brown Fish Owl	<i>Ketupa zeylonensis</i>	R	LC
65		Mottled Wood Owl	<i>Strix ocellata</i>	R	LC
66		Brown Wood Owl	<i>Strix leptogrammica</i>	R	LC
67		Indian Eagle Owl	<i>Bubo bengalensis</i>	R	LC
68		Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	R	LC
13. Order CAPRIMULGIFORMES					
69	20.Caprimulgidae	Sykes's Nightjar	<i>Caprimulgus mahrattensis</i>	WV	LC
70		Jungle Nightjar	<i>Caprimulgus indicus</i>	R	LC
14. Order APODIFORMES					
71	21.Apodidae	Asian Palm Swift	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i>	R	LC
15. Order UPUPIFORMES					
72	22.Upupidae	Common Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	R	LC
16. Order TROGONIFORMES					
73	23.Trogonidae	Malabar Trogon	<i>Harpactes fasciatus</i>	R	LC
17. Order CORACIFORMES					
74	24.Coraciidae	Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	R	LC
75	25.Alcedinidae	Common Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	R	LC
76	26.Halcyonidae	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	R	LC
77	27.Cerylidae	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	R	LC
78	28.Meropidae	Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	R	LC
79		Blue-bearded Bee-eater	<i>Nyctornis athertoni</i>	R	LC
18. Order BUCEROTIFORMES					
80	29.Bucerotidae	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	R	LC
81		Malabar Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros griseus</i>	R	LC
82		Malabar Pied Hornbill	<i>Anthracoceros coronatus</i>	R	NT
83		Great Hornbill	<i>Buceros bicornis</i>	R	NT
19. Order PICIFORMES					
84	30.Ramphastidae	White-cheeked Barbet	<i>Megalaima viridis</i>	R	LC
85		Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	R	LC
86	31.Picidae	Greater Goldenback	<i>Chrysocolaptes lucidus</i>	R	LC
87		Heart-spotted Woodpecker	<i>Hemicircus canente</i>	R	LC
88		Yellow-crowned Woodpecker	<i>Dendrocopos mahrattensis</i>	R	LC
20. Order PASSERIFORMES					
89	32.Aegithinidae	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	R	LC
90	33.Campephagidae	Black-headed Cuckooshrike	<i>Coracina melanoptera</i>	SV	LC
91		Small Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	R	LC
92		Orange Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i>	R	LC
93	34.Laniidae	Common Woodshrike	<i>Tephrodornis pondicerianus</i>	R	LC
94		Long-tailed Shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	R	LC
95	35.Dicruridae	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	R	LC
96		White-bellied Drongo	<i>Dicrurus caerulescens</i>	R	LC
97		Greater Racket-tailed Drongo	<i>Dicrurus paradiseus</i>	R	LC
98	36.Oriolidae	Indian Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus kundoo</i>	WV	LC
99		Black-hooded Oriole	<i>Oriolus xanthornus</i>	R	LC
100	37.Rhipiduridae	White-browed Fantail	<i>Rhipidura aureola</i>	R	LC
101	38.Monarchidae	Asian Paradise-flycatcher	<i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i>	R	LC
102		Black-naped Monarch	<i>Hypothymis azurea</i>	R	LC
103	39.Coridae	Rufous Treepie	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	R	LC
104		House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	R	LC

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Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	
				Migratory	IUCN
105		Indian Jungle Crow	<i>Corvus culminatus</i>	R	LC
106	40.Paridae	Great Tit	<i>Parus major</i>	R	LC
107		Indian Yellow Tit	<i>Parus aplonotus</i>	R	LC
108	41.Hirundinidae	Dusky Crag Martin	<i>Ptyonoprogne concolor</i>	R	NA
109		Red-rumped Swallow	<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	R	LC
110		Barn Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	WV	LC
111		Wire-tailed Swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	R	LC
112	42.Alaudidae	Malabar Lark	<i>Galerida malabarica</i>	R	LC
113	43.Pycnonotidae	Red-vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	R	LC
114		Red-whiskered Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	R	LC
115		Square-tailed Bulbul	<i>Hypsipetes ganeesa</i>	R	NA
116		Yellow-browed Bulbul	<i>Acritillas indica</i>	R	NA
117	44.Cistcolidae	Ashy Prinia	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	R	LC
118		Grey-breasted Prinia	<i>Prinia hodgsonii</i>	R	LC
119		Plain Prinia	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	R	LC
120		Jungle Prinia	<i>Prinia sylvatica</i>	R	LC
121	45.Sylvidae	Greenish Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus trochiloides</i>	WV	LC
122		Common Tailorbird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	R	LC
123	46.Timaliidae	Yellow-eyed Babbler	<i>Chrysomma sinense</i>	R	LC
124		Jungle Babbler	<i>Turdoides striata somervillei</i>	R	LC
125		Indian Scimitar Babbler	<i>Pomatorhinus horsfieldii</i>	R	LC
126		Large Grey Babbler	<i>Turdoides malcolmi</i>	R	LC
127		Brown-cheeked Fulvetta	<i>Alcippe poioicephala</i>	R	LC
128		Tawny-bellied Babbler	<i>Dumetia hyperythra</i>	R	LC
129	47.Zosteropidae	Oriental White-eye	<i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	R	LC
130	48.Sturnidae	Brahminy Starling	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i>	R	LC
131		Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	R	LC
132		Jungle Myna	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	R	LC
133		Chestnut-tailed Starling	<i>Sturnia malabarica</i>	WV	NA
134	49.Turdidae	Indian Blackbird	<i>Turdus simillimus</i>	SW	NA
135		Orange-headed (White throated) Thrush	<i>Zoothera citrina cyanotus</i>	R	LC
136		Malabar Whistling Thrush	<i>Myophonus horsfieldii</i>	R	LC
137		Blue Rock Thrush	<i>Monticola solitarius</i>	WV	LC
138		Blue-capped Rock Thrush	<i>Monticola cinclorhynchus</i>	WV	LC
139	50.Muscicapinae	Oriental Magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	R	LC
140		Indian Robin	<i>Saxicoloides fulicatus</i>	R	LC
141		Pied Bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	R	LC
142		Red-breasted Flycatcher	<i>Ficedula parva</i>	WV	LC
143		Asian Brown Flycatcher	<i>Muscicapa dauurica</i>	WV	LC
144		Tickell's Blue Flycatcher	<i>Cyornis tickelliae</i>	R	LC
145		White-rumped Shama	<i>Copsychus malabaricus</i>	R	LC
146		Taiga Flycatcher	<i>Ficedula albicilla</i>	WV	LC
147		Verditer Flycatcher	<i>Eumyias thalassinus</i>	WV	LC
148	51.Irenidae	Golden-fronted Leafbird	<i>Chloropsis aurifrons</i>	R	LC
149		Jerdon's Leafbird	<i>Chloropsis jerdoni</i>	R	LC
150	52.Dicaeidae	Thick-billed Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum agile</i>	R	LC
151		Nilgiri Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum concolor</i>	R	LC
152	53.Nectariniidae	Purple-rumped Sunbird	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i>	R	LC
153		Crimson-backed Sunbird	<i>Leptocoma minima</i>	R	NA
154		Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	R	LC
155		Loten's Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris lotenia</i>	R	NA
156		Vigors's Sunbird	<i>Aethopyga vigorsii</i>	R	NA

...Table 1. Showing avifauna recorded in Tillari and its vicinity

Sl. No.	Order/Family	Common Name	Scientific Name	Status	
				Migratory	IUCN
157	54. Passeridae	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	R	LC
158		Chestnut-shouldered Petronia	<i>Gymnoris xanthocollis</i>	R	LC
159	55. Ploceidae	Baya Weaver	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	R	LC
160		Indian Silverbill	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>	R	LC
161	56. Estrildidae	Red Avadavat	<i>Amandava amandava</i>	R	LC
162		Scaly-breasted Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	R	LC
163		White-rumped Munia	<i>Lonchura striata</i>	R	LC
164	57. Motacillidae	Grey Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	WV	LC
165		White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	WV	LC
166		White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	R	LC
167		Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	WV	LC
168		Citrine Wagtail	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	WV	LC
169		Forest Wagtail	<i>Dendronanthus indicus</i>	WV	LC
170		Tree Pipit	<i>Anthus trivialis</i>	WV	LC
171		Paddyfield Pipit	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	R	LC
172	58. Fringillidae	Common Rosefinch	<i>Carpodacus erythrinus</i>	WV	LC
173	59. Emberizidae	Black-headed Bunting	<i>Emberiza melanocephala</i>	WV	LC
174		Red-headed Bunting	<i>Emberiza bruniceps</i>	WV	LC

Note: Status 1. Migratory - R: Resident, WV: Winter visitor, SV: Summer visitor
 2. IUCN 2012 - V: Vulnerable, NT: Near Threatened, LC: Least concerned
 3. NA – IUCN assessment is not available

Table 2. Showing family wise number of bird species recorded in Tillari and its vicinity

Sl. No.	Name of the Family	Number of bird species recorded	Sl. No.	Name of the Family	Number of bird species recorded
1	Phasianidae	5	30	Ramphastidae	2
2	Anatidae	1	31	Picidae	3
3	Podicipedidae	1	32	Aegithinidae	1
4	Ciconiidae	2	33	Campephagidae	3
5	Threskiornithidae	2	34	Laniidae	2
6	Ardeidae	6	35	Dicruridae	3
7	Anhingidae	1	36	Oriolidae	2
8	Phalacrocoracidae	2	37	Rhipiduridae	1
9	Falconidae	2	38	Monarchidae	2
10	Accipitridae	12	39	Corvidae	3
11	Rallidae	2	40	Paridae	2
12	Burhinidae	1	41	Hirundinidae	4
13	Charadriidae	2	42	Alaudidae	1
14	Scolopacidae	6	43	Pycnonotidae	4
15	Laridae	1	44	Cistcolidae	4
16	Columbidae	10	45	Sylviidae	2
17	Psittacidae	2	46	Timaliidae	6
18	Cuculidae	5	47	Zosteropidae	1
19	Strigidae	5	48	Sturnidae	4
20	Caprimulgidae	2	49	Turdidae	5
21	Hemiprocnidae	1	50	Muscicapinae	9
22	Upupidae	1	51	Irenidae	2
23	Trogonidae	1	52	Dicaeidae	2
24	Coraciidae	1	53	Nectariniidae	5
25	Alcedinidae	1	54	Passeridae	2
26	Halcyonidae	1	55	Ploceidae	2
27	Cerylidae	1	56	Estrildidae	3
28	Meropidae	2	57	Motacillidae	8
29	Bucerotidae	4	58	Fringillidae	1
			59	Emberizidae	2
Total Number of birds					174

Images 1-6.

Malabar Pied Hornbill *Anthracoceros coronatus*

Indian Grey Hornbill *Ocyrceros birostris*

White Throated Thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus*

Black Drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*

Jungle babler *Turdoides striata somervillei*

Jungle babler *Turdoides striata somervillei*

recorded Malabar pied hornbill in association with Great hornbill and Malabar grey hornbill. For White throated thrush (*Zoothera citrina cyanotus*) and Jungle babler (*Turdoides striata somervillei*) we tried to identify sub species. Images 1-6 shows Malabar pied hornbill *Anthracoceros coronatus*, Indian grey hornbill *Ocyrceros birostris*, White throated thrush *Zoothera citrina cyanotus*, Black drongo *Dicrurus macrocercus*, Jungle babler *Turdoides striata somervillei*, Malabar Lark *Galerida malabarica* respectively recorded in the study area.

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Conflict of Interests:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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